

TANTANGAN ALUMNI PENDIDIKAN SOSIOLOGI MENGIKUTI SELEKSI PENDIDIKAN PROFESI GURU PRAJABATAN

Eva Fras Juiyanti Hutasoit¹, Joan Hesti Gita Purwasih²

^{1,2}Pendidikan Sosiologi, Universitas Negeri Malang
Jalan Semarang Nomor 5 Lowokwaru, Kota Malang, Jawa Timur, Indonesia

²e-mail: joan.hesti.fis@um.ac.id

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk menjelaskan tantangan yang dihadapi alumni Pendidikan Sosiologi Universitas Negeri Malang (UM) dalam mengikuti seleksi Pendidikan Profesi Guru (PPG) Prajabatan. Hasil penelitian penting dianalisis untuk mengetahui tingkat kesiapan alumni Pendidikan Sosiologi UM dalam mengikuti seleksi PPG Prajabatan. Tantangan atau kendala alumni juga penting diketahui agar mahasiswa Pendidikan Sosiologi UM lebih mempersiapkan diri menghadapi seleksi PPG Prajabatan. Jenis penelitian yang dilakukan adalah kualitatif deskriptif. Responden penelitian berjumlah 11 orang alumni Pendidikan Sosiologi UM. Teknik pengumpulan data menggunakan wawancara. Data dianalisis menggunakan model analisis interaktif yang terdiri dari pengumpulan data, reduksi data, penyajian data, dan verifikasi atau penarikan kesimpulan. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa penguasaan materi yang tidak maksimal dapat menjadi salah satu tantangan internal dan pelaksanaan tes substantif yang jauh dari domisili menjadi tantangan eksternal alumni Pendidikan Sosiologi UM.

Kata Kunci: Pendidikan Profesi Guru; alumni Pendidikan Sosiologi; tes substantif.

Abstract

The research aimed to explain the challenges faced by alumni of the Sociology Education State University of Malang (UM) in participating in the Education selection PreOccupational Teacher Profession (PPG). It is important to analyze the results of this research to determine the level of readiness of UM Sociology Education alumni to take part in the PPG PreOccupational selection. It is also important to know the challenges or constraints of alumni so that UM Sociology Education students are able to better prepare themselves for the future PPG PreOccupational selection. This type of research was descriptive qualitative. The number of research respondents was 11 alumni of Sociology Education State UM. Data collection techniques used interviews. Data were analyzed using an interactive analysis model consisting of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and verification or drawing conclusions. The results of the research showed that material mastery that is not optimal can be one of the internal challenges and the implementation of substantive tests that are far from their domicile is an external challenge for alumni of UM Sociology Education.

Keywords: Teacher Professional Education; Sociology Education alumni; substantive test.